

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13992361

Prioritizing Teacher Quality in Early Childhood Care and Education in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Early childhood care and education institutions are noted globally for their drives in developing the social, emotional and cognitive developments of learners as well as promoting in learners' behavioural attitudes that stimulate in them the curiosity for receptive embrace of formal primary education, developments that are solid foundations for the human capacity building and human capacity development of states in the future. As foundational as educational provision at this stage can be, governments in Nigeria do not participate directly in its provision, rather educational provision at this level is the exclusive reserve of the private investors, whose participation is solely driven by profit and not for quality service delivery. One area in which the profit-driven attitudes of the private investors has terribly compromised and undermined is teacher quality. Using the philosophical methodology, this study makes a strong case for prioritizing teacher quality in early childhood care and education in Nigeria. The paper recognizes the centrality of the teacher in any meaningful education and among other things make the following recommendations; government in Nigeria should participate in providing early childhood care and education, should direct teacher education institutions to establish departments of early childhood care and education in their various institutions and above all direct the private sector to establish early childhood care and education institution as part of their corporate social responsibility for promoting social justice, inclusion, equity and equality in Nigeria.

Keywords: Prioritizing, teacher quality, early childhood care and education, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, parents and the government of Nigeria are beginning to agree and align themselves on the critical role quality education can play in the overall development and survival of the individual and the collective survival of the state as an institution that is charged with the overall development and welfare of everybody and every institution in the state. Both parents and the Nigerian state embrace education as instrument and institution for empowering the individual and bringing about radical and revolutionary transformations of all the institutions and agencies in the state. Parents and the Nigerian state are guided by one common belief and motive namely the compass anyone can use in order to effectively and successfully navigate the twenty-first century with its potential promises and equally potential challenges is education. Education in the hands of parents and the Nigerian state is foundational in providing members of the Nigerian society basic and advanced skills and procedures for initiating creative thoughts that can help them venture into scientific and technological expeditions ranging from morally and sustainably exploiting and exploring the resources of the environment, ensuring improved human relations within and among nations, prioritizing political,

social and economic stability in states and globally as well as guaranteeing justice between individuals and individuals and between individuals and institutions of the state.

Parents and the Nigerian state equally embrace education as a sustainable instrument and institution for forming, reforming and transforming the individual and the Nigerian state from one level of growth and development to the other or put slightly different to transition a people and their state from a primitive, under-developed or under-developing to a modern or developed state. Part of the reason for the commitment of parents and the Nigerian state for using education in forming, reforming and transforming the individual and the Nigerian state is that as change is inevitable in the affairs of man and his institutions, any attempt at initiating change for the welfare of the individual and the Nigerian state must be routed through education before such change mantra or change agenda can become a reality.

The place of honour which education occupies can be appreciated in the remark credited to Shively (2005), when he writes that one essential social service that any responsible state provides for her citizens is education and no wonder the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) adopts education as an instrument par excellence for national development, and notes exceptionally that:

Education shall continue to be highly rated with national development plans because education is the most important instrument of change; any fundamental change in the intellectual and social outlook of any society has to be preceded by an educational revolution

Equally speaking in favour of the high regard parents have for education, Nwaokugha (2015:86) writes that:

Individuals (parents) consider education the best legacy and investment for their sons, daughter and wards and correspondingly parents consider themselves failures if they do not provide their sons, daughters and wards quality education. The commitment of parents in this direction can be seen in the extent in which they starve, go extra miles or indulge in humanly excruciating activities just to ensure that the mandate of providing quality education for their dependents is achieved.

The high regard that parents and the Nigerian state accord to education authoritatively derives from the position of the United Nations, which recognized education as a human rights. Education as a human rights according to Nwaokugha (2015:70) connotes an aura of sacredness which confers the provision of education to citizens as a fundamental natural right in which no one ought to be denied of. Part of the naturalness of education as a human right and why education must be provided for the people and not deny it from the people is that providing it to the citizens is a threshold and a basic entry point for the citizens' empowerment and acquisition of the fundamentals for effective, rational, critical, analytic and reflective thinking, development of ability to make choices or choose between alternatives and more pointedly the acquisition of skills that can enable citizens to take active part in the cultural, social, civil, political and democratic processes in their state.

The alignment of education to natural and human rights has created new awareness about education across the globe and that new awareness is tilted towards policy and axiological directions that makes case for education to be provided to the young ones prior to their entering primary school as a matter of right, equality and national development of states. In fact, the vision of providing instructional and educational experiences to the young ones prior to their attaining age six or entering primary school is a sound policy decision that targets raising a generation of interested, curious and enthusiastic learners for the primary school. This policy decision has a lot of positive implications for learners and the state just as it also has peculiarities and challenges across states. Of all the challenges and peculiarities that early childhood care and education faces in Nigeria, teacher quality stands out.

In any educational programme and initiative, teacher quality is a crucial entry point that can make or mar any education programme as teachers are the principal drivers or implementers of such programmes. In fact, well thought out and well-planned education programmes can terribly and abysmally fail when the issues that border on teacher quality are compromised or not adequately taken care of and not well thought out and not well-planned educational programmes have epically and

phenomenally succeeded when issues that border on teacher quality have been adequately taken care of. Nations, scholars and institutions acknowledge the critical and foundational roles of the teacher when they write that “no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers” (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004). As obvious as this can be, issues that border on teacher quality in Nigeria particularly at the early childhood care and education level is chokingly worrisome and phenomenally disturbing. It is as clear as day and night that most of the early childhood care and education centres and institutions in Nigeria do not have teachers who have the required and requisite educational qualifications to effectively handle learners at such critical and impressionable levels of education and most of such centres or institutions recruit secondary school leavers or university attended candidates who never graduated or who never had any formal professional certificates possibly because education at this level is solely operated by the private sector for business purposes.

This development undermines the importance of early childhood care and education in human capacity building and the national development of the Nigerian state as all the potential advantages that come with early childhood care and education may become illusions and distant dreams that hardly can translate into reality. Here lies the need for this study as the study has potentials to sensitize the Nigerian state in particular and humanity in general on the benefits of early childhood care and education programmes, can create awareness on how early childhood care and education can be an instrument or platform for making social justice a norm in Nigeria especially how inclusive and comprehensive access to early childhood care and education can be a catalyst for addressing and revolutionizing issues of intergenerational inequality at the social, economic, political and cultural capital levels that have become monumental in Nigeria and lastly the study can be of immense benefit to teacher education institutions in Nigeria and across the world that are charged with the responsibility of educating teachers who teach at early childhood care and education levels in the form of charting new curricular, administrative and pedagogically sound procedures and strategies for practitioners.

The theoretical framework upon which this study is based is social constructivism and social constructivism as an epistemological paradigm is a focal flashpoint in qualitative studies and strongly holds the view that human beings are key in the generation of knowledge and meaning through the process of interaction between human being’s experiences and ideas (Mogashoa, 2014). How this is translated into reality is highlighted by Nwaokugha & Abiakwu (2024:167) when they write that:

Social constructivism as a qualitative research paradigm works out best when the learner is actively engaged and committed to breaking new frontiers of knowledge, is committed to solving problems and responding to the demands of change, is desirous of collaborating with others as well as exploring and exhibiting the highest forms of creative and critical thinking.

One can therefore say that social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction makes case for the active engagement and active participation of persons who are curious and desirous of generating or expanding the frontiers of knowledge and this by extension suggests that when reference or focus is on the education industry, the learner or the student is the person who should show and demonstrate that active engagement, involvement or participation and should correspondingly be in the forefront of every teaching and learning activity. Basically, this study adopts the philosophical research methodology also known as qualitative research methodology, which is associated with many features and characteristics, principal among which is the gathering and “collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over an extended period in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other type of research” (Angadi, 2019:37), subjecting such gathered and collected narrative data to extensive analysis and from such analysis make rational and informed decisions that can lead to the resolution of crisis that has been the focus of the philosophical actions or endeavours, the methodology is often exploratory and aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational setting (Ishtiaq & Naz, 2024:10) and lastly prioritizing reflection, rigour of thought, meaningfulness or semantic clarity. These features and characteristics that are associated with the philosophical or qualitative research methodology are imbedded or incorporated in speculation, analysis and prescription which Nwaokugha & Danladi (2016), Nwaokugha & Ezeugwu

(2017) and Nwaokugha & Abiakwu (2017) are specific and unique methods of carrying out philosophical or qualitative research.

Speculation as a philosophical or qualitative method of carrying out research has been in vogue in the past and is still relevant in the present as it constantly reinvents itself in new forms in the world of knowledge and what attests to this is the level of attention that scholars give to it. Speculation or speculative thinking according to Haung, Xie & Chen (2021:1) refers to thinking about past and future possibilities, which includes counterfactual thinking, prefactual and other types of thinking. One key point which attracts scholars to speculation and speculative thinking is the fact that speculative thinking is associated with improving performances or actions in the future. Because speculation or speculative thinking is committed to ensuring quality reforms, transformations and innovations in the future, Taggart (2012) writes that speculation or speculative thinking aims at providing man and his institutions with higher-order consolation, in fact, a kind of philosophy of action that is committed to shaping and influencing peoples' philosophies of life and public philosophy and correspondingly serves as a provocateur. The central, critical, creative and overarching significance of speculation and speculative thinking in the world of knowledge in particular and the general affairs of man and his institutions is carefully highlighted by Gare (2020) in these words:

Speculation is primordial to all experience and thinking revealing..... the possibility of elaborating alternative metaphors frees us not only from these dead metaphors... opening up new possibilities for enquiry, but the possibility of reconceiving ourselves and our place in nature. In this way, speculation makes it possible to transform ourselves, creating radically new ways of living and new forms of life. On this view, speculation, by opening new possibilities could free us from the destructive trajectories of current civilization.

That speculation is primordial to all experience and thinking can be attested to in the remark by Currie (2021) when he writes that speculation is critical for successful science, egregious as well as productive. Practically, to indulge in speculation or speculative thinking according to Oduor (2010:97) is to wonder, conjecture, guess or to hypothesize. Guided by the same line of thought, Aminigo (1999) and Agulanna (2011) in their separate studies writes that speculation is an attempt to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought.

The modus operandi of speculation or speculative thinking as a philosophical or qualitative method of research according to Nwaokugha & Keri-Frank (2023:39) is

One in which a scholar who is favourably disposed to using it builds up ideas and carefully, sequentially, systematically and logically shows how one idea is logically and systematically related to the other ideas in the whole system of ideas.

What the above points hands to is that the foundational idea of speculation as a method of philosophical research is deep rooted in what Nwaokugha & Wogonwu (2023:4) call "a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse" and on the basis of the above, effective use of logic and effective use of language are foundational in clarifying assumptions, pressing out meanings and demonstrating rigours of thought that can lead to the establishment of facts. On the other hand, the ever-presence or consistency of speculation as a philosophical research method in particular and in the knowledge industry is hinged on man's innate desire and curiosity to know especially realities that continuously exert influence on man and his institutions, yet lack definite universal explanation, so attempts to know, explain and understand reality are at the centre or heart of speculation and this lends credence to the age long saying that people speculate in order to know and logically the more people speculate on a particular subject matter, the more they are likely to break epistemological frontiers concerning the subject matter so far they speculate upon. In fact, Swedberg (2021) says it all when he writes that people speculate when faced with realities that are ultimately unknown to them and this provides sound justifications why axiological topics namely social philosophy, ethics, aesthetics as well as political philosophy and metaphysical topics are at the heart of speculation and speculative thinking. Axiological and metaphysical topics are vibrantly and robustly attractive to speculation simply

because they lack a one size fits all answer or interpretation, they are constantly changing in time and space (Nwaokugha & Keri-Frank, 2023) and correspondingly are superlatively receptive to change, where practitioners or specialists in the fields present what they feel may be right base on the circumstances at the moment and are also ready to speculate and change their positions in line with what may prevail in the future.

Analysis as a method of carrying out philosophical research focuses on exposing, revealing and pressing out whatever meanings that may be associated with a word, term, concept and proposition in any context such word, term, concept and proposition may be used. The analyst who uses analysis is principally concerned with the meanings that may be imbedded or associated with the words, terms, concepts and propositions in any piece of presentation and the reason for making the meanings of words, terms, concepts and propositions flashpoints in the process of analysis is that words, terms, concepts and propositions are the vehicle and instrument for communicating ideas and the basis upon which meanings are derived, implying that the level of emphasis placed on a particular word, term, concept and proposition is critical and instructive in determining and influencing its meaning in that particular context. Analysis is undertaken in philosophical researches to clarify ambiguities, contradictions, absurdities and possibly to call attention to the meaning of word, term, concept and proposition that may be the focus of a particular discussion. In fact, analysis targets precision in whatever meaning the analyst intends to project or more precisely ideas wherever they are presented must be presented in clear, concise and unambiguous ways. It is an open secret that virtually all misunderstandings, crises, disagreements and conflicts owe their root causes to faulty use of language or faulty communication and where analysis is properly done, it helps to bring to the barest minimum the occurrence of conflicts, crises, misunderstanding and disagreement. What this reveals is that analysis is key to making peace and harmonious living a norm across the globe.

According to Nwaokugha & Abiakwu (2024:167), analysis is of two types namely conceptual analysis and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis involves that type of analysis that primarily focuses on ascertaining whether the meaning that is attached to a word, term, and concept represents what that word, term and concept stands for while any analysis that prioritized ascertaining if the meaning ascribed to a sentence is really what the sentence stands for is linguistic analysis. Any scholar who employs the analytic method according to Nwaokugha & Danladi (2016:421) “starts by breaking down his subject matter into smaller units that constitute it and at the same time shows how all are related in attaining a specific objective”.

The 21st century has been spectacular in the breaking of epistemological frontiers across discipline in both developed, developing and under-developed world and what has made this possible has been the embrace of analysis or the analytic method by scholars in their pursuit and search for knowledge. In fact, the trending practice in scholarship all over the world is one where analysis is fast replacing other methods of research, suggesting that through analysis, more epistemological frontiers can be broken and humanity can enjoy more global peace as well as more dividends of their investments in education and research.

Prescription as a philosophical research methodology invokes a meaning that revolves around the conscious, systematic, logical and coherent process of establishing standards and criteria for judging values or making prescriptive value judgment. It is on the basis of this that Oduor (2010) writes that prescription can be fixed or located in the same semantic environment as to recommend or set down as a rule or guide for judging human actions and Nwaokugha (2021:102) is straight to the point when he writes that prescription:

Is achieved in a research in the form of a researcher making autonomous value statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be resolved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed. In a way, suggestions and recommendations in researches and other forms of writing fall within the frame of reference of prescription.

We can say and say it very strongly that prescription is at the heart of every research as every research target solving or resolving one problem or the other and concrete and identifiable lines of actions for solving and resolving such identified problem are what prescription focuses attention on. As obvious as the above remark can be, there are disciplines and scholars that prescription is a creative and

critical article of faith and a tool without which their professional practice and usefulness to man in particular and society generally is incomplete. Scholars who major in axiology especially social philosophy, aesthetics, ethics and political philosophy cannot be effective in their professional practice without prescription and the reason why this is so, is that values in the affairs of man and his society are not fixed and cannot be fixed, as they are constantly changing in time and space, and correspondingly demand from those who are experts in it or who discuss it to receptively respond to issues of values based on the degree of change that is prevalent at the point in time and also be ready to be guided by change in subsequent discussions of value in the future.

As every branch of knowledge benefits from rigorous inquiry and philosophical reflections (Nwoke & Nwaokugha, 2024), which are inherent features of philosophical or qualitative research, thus studies as indicated earlier used the philosophical or qualitative methodology and its use in this study is justifiable. The philosophical or qualitative research methodology has in recent time become the trending paradigm and a destination of choice by scholars and researchers due to its versatility in triggering ground breaking breakthroughs across disciplines especially in the twenty-first century. The truth of this assertion has been acknowledged by Nwaokugha & Ihuoma (2019:277) when they write that the philosophical or qualitative research methodology raises scholars and researchers' curiosity into investigating and breaking new frontiers of knowledge, in addition to boosting:

The confidence levels of researchers as researchers see every challenge in any academic discipline as solvable and resolvable. In fact, philosophical research method of enquiry stimulates in scholars the desire to critically and continuously try out new academic options that can result in phenomenal improvements of scholars and the breaking of new frontiers of knowledge.

What can be considered more robust, detailed and comprehensive justifications why scholars contemporarily embrace the philosophical or qualitative research methodology is provided by Nwaokugha & Danladi (2016:421) in these words:

Indulgence or embrace of philosophical research methods affords freedom and opportunity that invite, motivates and challenge researchers to venture into problem areas across disciplines. By this feature researchers are availed platforms which in addition to tackling diversified subject matters also promote progress in the form of extending and breaking new frontiers of knowledge. The issue of diversified subject matters and the dividends thereof are possible because, philosophical research methods produce and rely more on theories than any other research method. What is implicated here is that philosophical research method is not restricted and consequently does not in any way impoverish researchers and disciplines that are favourably disposed to using it. It rather contributes in ground breaking breakthroughs in the knowledge industry. All these by implication mean that the knowledge industry and mankind can be better off in terms of opportunities and dividends associated with research, its contributions to improving human conditions and acquisition of knowledge.

A norm among scholars and researchers who use the philosophical research methodology is to create adequate awareness and in-depth insights on the key concepts and terms that are the focus of a study or investigation and to this we now turn.

Early Childhood Care and Education

Globally, what scholars, institutions and states call early childhood care and education is a conglomerate of custodial, surveillance and rudimentary instructional activities and practices that take place simultaneously (Nwaokugha, 2016) that are focused on the young ones whose ages range from 0-5 years prior to their admission into the primary school. Such custodial, surveillance and instructional activities and practices upon which early childhood care and education semantically and thematically revolves aims "to promote the physical, cognitive and social development of children" (Ghosh, 2021:7260) so as to trigger in the young ones' curiosity and readiness for formal educational activities at the primary school level. The emphasis in promoting the physical cognitive and social development of children is deep rooted in the fact that children whose early childhood experiences and developments have been rightly kick-started and placed on the right tracks have been provided all what it takes to sustainably do well in the pursuits of formal learning and survival in the future.

The specific age brackets of 0-5 years that early childhood care and education focuses attention on is responsible for scholars', institutions and states' definition of the concept as any care and educational provisions and experiences that are provided for children before their admission into the primary school. In Nigeria, where care and educational activities for the young ones prior to their admission into the primary school goes by the name pre-primary education, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004:11) lists the objectives to be achieved from pre-primary education to include conscious and deliberate efforts to:

- (a) Effect a smooth transition from the home to the school
- (b) Prepare the child for the primary level of education
- (c) Provide adequate care and supervision for the children while their parents are at work (on the farms, in the markets, offices etc)
- (d) Inculcate social norms
- (e) Inculcate in the child the spirit of enquiry and creativity through the exploration of nature, the environment, art, music and play with toys, etc.
- (f) Develop a sense of cooperation and team spirit
- (g) Learn good habits especially good health habits, and
- (h) Teach the rudiments of numbers, letters, colours, shapes, forms etc through play.

Early childhood institutions and centres maintain unique features and characteristics when it comes to methods of instruction. Institutions and centres that are guided by the core philosophical underpinnings of early childhood development and correspondingly achieve the best from early childhood care education and development are those whose structures are flexible in addition to maintaining humane baby friendly and learner friendly teaching and learning environment. Teaching and learning learner friendly environment is inclusive of motherly care, humane, respect-giving, peaceful and professional dispositions, which the teacher and the other personnel in such centres and institutions are to display vis-à-vis the orderly arrangements of specific and general infrastructure ranging from seats, tables, chairs, toys and other objects that learners use for play.

Across states, institutions and centres that provide care and education for the young ones prior to their entry or admission into the primary school go by different names such as crèche, daycare, pre-nursery, pre-primary, head-start, kindergarten (Nwaokugha, 2016) and no two states have a uniform practice in terms of how their early childhood educational arrangements or services is provided. What seems to account for the sophistication or otherwise of early childhood education model that is provided across states is the level of developmental sophistication of the individual states, the level of commitment of the individual states in terms of social welfare programmes and social justice programmes or initiatives and most importantly the level of economic buoyancy and commitment of parents in providing this critical and all important level of education for their sons, daughters and wards.

In early childhood education institutions and centres, care and education come up in a manner where focus is on one before the other. Fundamentally, care is the starting point and involves surveillance of the adult over the younger person for the reasons of providing security, protection and keeping the younger one safe from harm and danger. This is the reason why young ones who benefit from care are those from ages 0-3, an observation that prompts Hayes (2007) to note that care is custodial in tone. Anyone who critically observes what happens in early childhood care and education can quickly notice a systematic transition from one to the other, notably from care to education. On the other hand, education in the context of early childhood care, education and development invokes a meaning that points in the direction of formalized teaching and learning in a school-like setting (Urban, 2009), where focus is on developing higher order activity or creative and critical thinking skills that targets promoting continuous learning in the younger ones especially aspects of rudimentary learning that can stimulate in the learners the ability to respond to challenges they find in environment in which they find themselves. Education is provided to the younger ones from the ages of 3-5. In simple analytic terms, it can be correct to say that care and education in the context of early childhood development travels on the same road but according to Nwaokugha (2016) both maintain different speed, rhythm, depth and more importantly do not target the same destination. There is interest in investment in early childhood care and education especially in this twenty-first century. In fact, the present level of

awareness and seriousness that is given to early childhood care and education across the globe derives justification from the realization that investments in early childhood care and education is a necessary foundation and condition for human capacity building and the national development of any state as products of early childhood care and education centres and institutions are automatically the leaders of tomorrow, meaning that achieving the tomorrow or future of our dreams is absolutely dependent on how the present generation positions and invests in the young ones of today. The extent in which the present generation can raise a generation of young ones that can bequeath to humanity a future that conveniently and robustly represents, captures and reflects the all-encompassing and all-inclusive aspirations of a complex and ever-changing twenty-first century is absolutely dependent on teacher quality in the various early childhood care and education centres and institutions particularly in Nigeria. In the section that follows, detailed attention shall be given to teacher quality in early childhood care and education centres and institutions in Nigeria.

Teacher Quality in Early Childhood Care and Education Institutions in Nigeria

Anyone who has a vast and robust knowledge of the complex act of teaching and learning or knowledge of human capacity development for short, can quickly admit that sufficient credits must go to teachers who teach learners in the learners' delicate period of early development. Teachers who teach learners during learners' earliest developmental stages play crucial roles in influencing and determining what becomes of the learner in terms of developing the learners' cognitive capability, the learners' curiosity and receptivity to learning and responses to traits that are associated with positive human development. Such teachers, it must be acknowledged lay the foundational trajectories of whatever happens to the state at large. This simply means any society that makes the right investments in its early childhood care and education sector may have sustainably and strongly laid foundations for raising generations of its citizens who can cater for its human development and human capacity building needs in the future. It is from the angle of the benefits that derive from early childhood care and education particularly for the learners that Inder and Ramanujan (2024:91) write that quality early childhood care and education (ECCE) can lead to long term positive outcomes for children and by extension to the human capacity and human development drives of the state. Such positive aura or development revolves around the fact that early childhood care and education is instrumental for the cognitive, social and emotional development of the individual that in turn becomes the foundational pillars in the learners' quest and curiosity for lifelong learning skills and capabilities.

On the other hand, any state that undermines or compromises investments in its early childhood care and education may have automatically depleted the foundations for raising a generation of its citizens who can trigger and boost its human development and human capacity needs. In fact, any act of compromise in investment decisions that concerns investments in the early childhood care and education of a state is a recipe for failure in all the indexes for measuring quality and durable advancement of a people and their state.

Getting it right in terms of laying the right foundations for the cultivation of the right behavioural dispositions that can trigger the right cognitive curiosity in learners in early childhood care and education institutions means that the right calibre of teachers must be available and at the same time, committed, dedicated and intellectually, methodologically and pedagogically sound so as to have the capacity and capability to deliver and the government, private investor or whosoever that is in charge of providing such early childhood care and education must play his or her part without compromise. A teacher is a person who enrolled and received professional education in a teacher education institution or other designated centres that are affiliated to teacher education institutions and whose quality of professional education enables him or her after the completion of the teacher education programme to function at multiple levels such as providing pedagogical instructions that targets stimulating in learners the ability and capacity to learn, knowledge that enables him or her to serve as a bridge builder between learners and learners, between learners and parents, between educational institutions and other institutions in the state and above all professionally possessing good knowledge of a subject matter or matters, good knowledge of the learner, the society as well as knowledge of how to methodologically manipulate the environment to stimulate in learners the curiosity, capacity, capability and enthusiasm to learn.

Whom the teacher is and the inclusiveness of the professional education of the teacher makes him or her a key and indispensable asset in the national development discourse of states globally so much that there can be no development of any configuration – social, political, moral, cultural, economic, philosophical, artistic, scientific and technological that can take place without the teacher. The territorial and epistemological space in which the professional education of the teacher covers has prompted many states to conclude that any state that compromises its teacher education or the quality of its teachers has consciously introduced viruses and setbacks in her human capacity building machinery and national development. All these point in one direction, namely, the quality of the teacher or teacher quality in the education system of a state is the most important factor upon which the quality and standard of education and correspondingly the quality of development in any state can be judged. The place of quality, quality teachers or teacher quality has been highlighted by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004), when it writes that “no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers and Nwaokugha (2014:15) says it all when he writes that:

The teacher is so fundamental that he is at the centre of all reforms and innovations in education to the point that “perfect” educational policies and programmes with corresponding financial backings can translate to nothing if teachers who are the implementers and drivers of the policies in the education industry are not in adequate supply, committed and dedicated.

What all the above exposes is that teacher quality is key and central to achieving all the good (positive) things in education and at the same time is held responsible for igniting and influencing bad and negative things that happen in the field of education. In fact, it is an irrefutable assertion that the successes and failures which students, schools and by implication the quality of critical, creative and progressive ideas which products of educational institutions initiate across the world owe their roots to teacher quality in the various educational institutions which such learners passed through. Tabé (2023:487) hints at this when he writes that “despite robust compelling reasons like social injustice resulting from historical imbalances and parental factors, teacher quality remains the most talked about issue by scholars”. This means that the capacity of the education industry to realize all its manifest and latent functions strongly depends on teacher quality. In all of these a million dollars question can be: What exactly is teacher quality?

Teacher quality according Alvarez (2008:15) is a broad concept with little consensus concerning its precise definition. Such assertion about teacher quality as claimed by Alvarez (2008) may be revealing and what it reveals is that different scholars may have one thing or the other to say about it and the concept may also be one of those concepts whose meanings can manifest or open up better when it has been thoroughly analyzed. Alvarez (2008:15) is one scholar who documents that teacher quality refers to a professional who recognizes the students’ educative needs, possesses specific teaching skills and knows how to assist students learning need while Sani, Shaibu and Melaiye (2020:166) write that teacher quality comprises of teacher attributes which include teacher qualification, exposure on job training, practices and effectiveness on the job.

Anyone who critically and unbiasedly examines the above definitions of teacher quality as provided by the above scholars can notice that teacher quality preoccupies itself with identifiable professional qualities, competencies and effective measures which a teacher can possess for enhancing the quality of his or her service delivery or invokes a meaning that revolves around inherent professional attributes which a practicing teacher can possess to enhance his service delivery, effectiveness, and competence in the teaching learning situation. In some scholars curiosity to discuss teacher quality and such inherent professional attributes which a practicing teacher can have or possess so as to enhance his service delivery, such scholars independently and autonomously introduce variables which when viewed critically and rationally can belong to bracket of variables that reflect teacher quality but which another scholar that earlier discussed the concept may not include. This simply means that there are variable in the definition of teacher quality that may be present in the definition of the concept provided by one scholar, which another scholar who had discussed the same concept may not include.

An inclusive and comprehensive definition of teacher quality can portray the concept as a conglomerate of inherent professional personal attributes which an individual practicing teacher is

capable of possessing so much that such attributes help him to pedagogically demonstrate some high profile level of effectiveness and competence that can trigger higher productivity in his learners and such variables that constitute indexes for determining teacher quality include possession of professional qualification and certification, rigour and thoroughness in teacher preparation and training, teachers' cognitive ability, teachers' commitment and dedication to professionalism and professional practice, teachers' knowledge of subject matter, teachers' knowledge of the psychology of the learners, quality of instruction teachers are capable of producing, educational background of the teacher, levels of professional development of the teacher while in service, robust and sound knowledge of methodologies of delivery of instruction to learners, level of students' academic achievement, availability of infrastructure and conduciveness of the environment where the teacher works and more importantly proficiency or expertise in the management and coordination of human and material resources that are available in the school – in all, teacher quality is all about attributes that enhances a teachers' efficiency, effectiveness and increase in productivity in teaching and learning which a teacher should possess. Put slightly different, teacher quality is inclusive and comprehensive in outlook and in these outlooks revolves around all the indexes and attributes for ensuring teacher effectiveness, efficiency and quality service delivery so that all the predetermined goals and objectives set out and identified by institutions and states for meeting the needs of the individual and those of the state human capacity building and development, national development, meeting and improving human conditions or perfect and superlative pursuits of human excellence targeted through the teacher for the common survival of the state and humanity.

It has to be said in unambiguous terms that responsible states make teacher quality a topmost priority in any policy formulation and innovation in the education industry and this priority is anchored on the fact that the dreams of any state for the development of the people and the state can translate to nothing where there are no quality teachers to translate such dreams into reality and parents key into this as teacher quality in a school is a major consideration which influence parents in their choice of school for their children. What demonstrates that the seal of teacher quality or quality teacher is in a school or educational system is the ability of the teachers to use a variety of instructional methodologies and materials in their teaching to stimulate the learners to learn and proofs that all the expected cognitive objectives that the teacher wants the learners to achieve have been achieved and can be practically and theoretically demonstrated through the behaviours of the learners. This is where academic achievement of learners is a litmus test and index for assessing and confirming teacher quality in a school or educational system.

Having laid bare the attributes that make up or constitute teacher quality, another million dollars question is: To what extent has the Federal Government of Nigeria ensured that teachers in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria comply with possessing such attributes, which teachers in early childhood care and education institutions should possess? The history of early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria is unique: unique in the sense that it is an entirely private sector affair and this is a reflection of the policy direction of the government of Nigeria. There have been several policy summersaults in education in Nigeria that has come to settle with the government's open acknowledgement that it cannot solely provide education for Nigerians and correspondingly "voluntary agencies and groups shall be allowed to establish schools with minimum standards laid down by the federal government".

Following the above position and out of intellectual curiosity, there has been divided opinions among scholars on the right description or tag that can be given to the invitation or involvement of the private sector in educational provision in Nigeria; some scholars maintain that it is a rescue mission and a bailout mechanism since the federal government has failed to provide for its citizens one of the most basic social goods that a responsible government should provide while others say that it is a business outfit and a capitalist adventure for profit and exploitation of the people. Anyone who is familiar with the situation of things in Nigeria particularly in education and human capital development sector can simply admit that the participation of the private sector in education and its provision is purely for business and profit maximization because the education sector in Nigeria is more of an unexplored market where the products (the learners) are in abundance and correspondingly waiting to be tapped and what attests to the above claim is the remark by Nwaokugha (2015:78), who cited Nigeria

Television Authority (NTA) Network News of September, 9th 2013, as having reported that 10.5 out of 31 million out of school children in Sub-Saharan Africa is in Nigeria. It is no surprise that majority of the figure above can be in the age bracket of learners who should be in the early childhood care and education institutions.

Of all the levels of education in Nigeria, the Federal Republic of Nigeria made the early childhood care and education level the exclusive reserve of the private sector, with its responsibility to that level of education succinctly put this way:

The responsibility of government for the pre-primary education shall be to promote the training of qualified pre-primary school teachers in adequate number, contribute to the development of suitable curriculum, supervise and control the quality of such institutions and establish pre-primary sections in existing schools. (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2004:11)

The neglect and ceding of a foundational and critical level of education that is necessary and fundamental for the cognitive, emotional and social development of the child (learner) on one hand and a route for raising the child's (learner's) curiosity for a receptive embrace of formal primary education to the private sector is revealing and what it reveals is the lackadaisical attitude of the Nigerian state towards education, an attitude which Emenyonu (1994) says is one in which education is made to be one social provision that is irrelevant to Nigeria's national development. This regrettable attitude of the Nigerian state towards education generally is a testimony that all the oversight functions particularly the training of qualified pre-primary school teachers the Nigerian state plans for the early childhood care and education sector that is exclusively in the hands of the private sector whose involvement and participation in education is for profit maximization and exploitative cut-throat capitalism cannot see the light of the day.

As the private investors invest in the education industry because of the monetary rewards that education can quickly generate (Nwaokugha, 2015:78), most of such educational institutions in Nigeria in which early childhood care and education top their list,

Characteristically exist in dilapidated structures, are usually operated in buildings not purposefully built for the purposes of school infrastructure and not licensed by the government as a school hence they exist secretly and illegally. In practical terms, those private schools which exist in huts, warehouses and in residential houses in towns, urban centers and villages across Nigeria readily come to mind here and they disastrously lack the serenity and intellectual spirit expected of schools (Nwaokugha, 2015:78)

Also, the declaration by the Federal Government of Nigeria that it will establish pre-primary sections in existing public schools" (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004), which it has not done till today is a reflection, and demonstration of federal government of Nigeria's neglect and lackadaisical attitudes towards education generally and early childhood care and education in particular. The most phenomenal and most serious act of neglect which the Nigerian government has demonstrated towards early childhood care and education is in the area of teachers and teacher quality. As a sector of education that is operated by the private investors whose sole interests is profit maximization, such investors hardly deem it necessary and essential to recruit the right calibre of teachers who can lay the right foundations at this formative, delicate and critical level of education that is determinant in determining the life of the learner and the future of his state.

It has to be admitted that specialist teachers in the area of early childhood care and education in Nigeria is terribly in short supply and this is made more complex by the inability of teacher education institutions in Nigeria to establish departments of early childhood care and education as well as the inability to the few existing ones to increase their admission quotas into various sub-units in their various departments. What has become the norm in early childhood care and education in Nigeria is a situation where there is acute lack of qualified teachers and the profit minded orientation and capitalist inclinations of the private sector investors in the sector make them to capitalize on profit maximization as against employing capable and qualified teachers into their establishments. The consequence of this unfortunate development is that teacher quality in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria is terribly compromised. What the private investors in the sector

embrace to be a bailout or a response to the situation, though ingloriously, is pictorially and graphically captured by Nwaokugha (2015:79) when he writes that:

What obtains is that anyone who aspires to teach is employed by the management or proprietor and most private schools (early childhood care and education centres) in this category have become goldmines and employment destinations for candidates who claim they attended universities or any post-secondary educational institutions but never had certificates. In some cases, holders of questionable secondary school certificates are employed as teachers.

Compounding the teacher quality issue in early childhood care and education institutions in Nigeria are issues that border on poor pay, denial of benefits and lack of respect and recognition for the available teachers in the system. The profit-oriented philosophy and mindset of investors in early childhood care and education has made poverty, denial of benefits and lack of respect and recognition norms among teachers in early childhood care and education institution due to the poor salary that the teachers receive from those who employed them. Poor salaries, denial of benefits and recognition for early childhood care and education teachers seem to be a global phenomenon as studies conducted by Whitebook, Mclean, Austin & Edward (2019) and Kim, Brand & Zeltzer (2024), all report low salaries, denials of benefits and lack of respect and recognition as serious challenges that teachers in early childhood care and education institutions face. Such challenges have the capacity to negatively influence the quality of commitment and dedication of the teachers, a development that has strong potentials to affect the quality of care and education such teacher can provide and by extension quality of national development of the state.

Scholars have given reason for the general neglect and lackadaisical attitudes of Nigeria towards early childhood care and education in Nigeria. According to Asodike and Abdulrahman (2013:345).

Issue related to early childhood education in Nigeria at present is not appreciated as a national responsibility. There is no gain saying the fact that government has not demonstrated a serious commitment to education of children between the ages of 0-3 and 3-5 years

CONCLUSION

No education system can effectively and efficiently function without teachers and this has been recognized globally with the acknowledgement that no education system anywhere in the world can arise above the quality of the teachers who operate the education system. What this reveals is that the efficiency and effectiveness of any education system to produce the right calibre of manpower upon which the sustainable development of any state hinges heavily depends on the quality of teachers that teach in the education system and for teachers in the education system to superlatively and qualitatively deliver depends on teacher quality or quality of teachers in the education system. Teacher quality is an umbrella term and a conglomerate of inherent professional attributes that cut across the ability of teachers in the education system to possess the required and requisite educational qualifications and certifications, rigour and thoroughness in teacher preparation and training, the ability of the teacher to have the right cognitive ability, teachers' commitment and dedication to professionalism, ethical uprightness and professional practice, teachers' knowledge of their subject matter, teachers' knowledge of the psychology of the learner and knowledge of the variables that promote and inhibit learning, quality of constructive instruction that teachers are capable of providing to learners, level of professional development of the teacher while in service, teachers' demonstration of methodological expertise in the delivery of instruction to learners, levels of students' academic achievements and more importantly degree of mastery, effectiveness and proficiency in the coordination and management of human and material resources that are available in the school where the teacher teaches.

One condition and one litmus test for ascertaining teacher quality in the education system is the extent in which such attributes of the teacher as identified above can theoretically and practically transform the teaching learning space and correspondingly enhance and promote learners' maximum educational attainment and performance that altogether can trigger and stimulate higher academic achievement in

the learners. Because whatever dreams of states for development can be achieved through the teacher, teacher quality is a serious consideration in educational policy formulations and decisions of states. However, the high regard for teacher quality does not receive commensurate attention in some states especially at the early childhood care and education level and part of why this is so is that the provision of education at this level is exclusively in the hands of the private sectors, whose objective for investing in education is for profit – the monetary rewards that are ever present that assure maximum turn-over for whosoever invests in the education industry.

Being so driven by profit motives, there must be many areas of compromise and in the case of Nigeria, teacher quality is one focal area. It has been established that early childhood care and education section is foundational in developing the learners' social, hygienic, emotional and cognitive abilities as well as has the ability to trigger and stimulate the learners' receptivity for the embrace of formal primary education but despite laying the foundations for the learners' educational pursuits, the neglect and lackadaisical attitudes of Nigeria to it especially on issues that border on teacher quality is phenomenally regrettable. Contrary to the sector having the best hands in terms of teachers, the sector has turned out to be gold mines and employment destinations for people who have questionable certificates and questionable professional training so much that the majority of teachers at this critical and sensitive level of education are people who claim they attended universities or other post-secondary educational institutions but never formally graduated. Because of the class of teachers at this level of education in Nigeria and the profit drives of the investors, the pay for the teachers is extremely poor, a development that causes the teachers to withdraw their commitment and dedication to duty. Proof of the teachers' withdrawal of commitment and dedication to duty can be noticed in their continuous search for job and persistence submission of applications for employment to other early childhood care and education institutions even when they are in the employment and pay roll of another.

As a bid to address some of the unfortunate developments in the early childhood care and education sector in Nigeria, it is necessary and fundamental that we make some suggestions and recommendations. The decision and action of the Federal Government of Nigeria to leave the provision of education at this critical and formative stages of the learners in the hands of the private sector or private investors should be condemned in its entirety and federal, states and local governments should be reminded that their inability to participate in the provision of early childhood care and education is equivalent to building castles without foundations and this has potentials to frustrate whatever good plans they may have from the primary to the tertiary levels that concern quality human capital development. In fact, the foundation that the private sector or private investors may be providing cannot be inclusive as majority of Nigerians cannot afford to pay at the exorbitant and cut throat capitalist orientation that the private sector may provide their services.

The Government of Nigeria at all level should regulate what happens in early childhood care and education institutions especially issues that border on teacher quality. The idea that anyone can teach at this critical and formative level of education should be rejected. Alternatively, a minimum of a first degree in early childhood care and education should be the benchmark.

The Government should direct all the faculties of education in all tertiary education institutions in Nigeria to establish department of early childhood care and education, with a mandate to produce qualified teachers who can effectively and professionally teach at this level of education.

The private sector should be directed to establish early childhood care and education centres and institutions as part of their corporate social responsibility and drive towards human capacity building and human capacity development. Such drives can be used to intensify the pursuit and establishment of social security measures such as social justice, inclusion, equity and equality in Nigeria.

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